

Balancing Crisis Resolution Speed and Sustainability: Autocratic, Laissez-Faire, Transformational Leadership in Crisis Management

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Abstract:

This study compares autocratic, laissez-faire, transformational leadership in crisis management. The focus of this study is on balancing speed and sustainability. Result analysis show that autocratic leaders address crises quickly but engages in risks, laissez-faire leaders are ineffective due to lack of direction, transformational leaders drives sustainable improvements with high engagement hip in crisis management. Findings suggest context-driven leadership in crises. Findings suggest that autocratic leadership and speed has a strong positive correlation($r=0.8$). Transformational leadership and sustainability has a strong positive correlation($r=0.85$). Laissez-faire leadership and ineffectiveness has a strong positive correlation($r=0.9$). t test shows a significant difference ($p<0.05$) in employee satisfaction among autocratic vs transformational leaders. t test also reveals a significant difference ($p<0.01$) between transformational vs laissez-faire leaders. Analysis of ANOVA shows a significant difference in leadership styles' impact on crisis outcomes ($F=12.5, p<0.01$). Analysis reveals that transformational leadership is most effective in crisis management, balancing speed and sustainability with high employee satisfaction. Autocratic leadership shows quicker but less sustainable results, while laissez-faire leadership is least effective.

Keywords: Autocratic, Laissez-Faire, Transformational Leadership Styles, Crisis Management

Introduction:

Leadership styles play a pivotal role in navigating organizations through crisis. This study examines the efficacy of autocratic, laissez-faire and transformational leadership in balancing speed and sustainability during crisis management. There are different types of leadership styles. Autocratic leaders implement strict protocols immediately and address crisis quickly but engages in risk. Organization production quality improves within a short time, but employees feel demotivated, citing lack of input. They prefer rapid fix employees, but risk demotivating staff. Transformational leaders involve teams in identifying problem-solving, they try to understand the root causes and

solutions, and they also foster sustainable improvements and boost engagements at the work place. They inspire employees towards commitment to quality at work. Under these leadership employees felt engaged and committed to quality improvements. Transformational leadership encourages employee performance and organizational success.

Literature Review:

Singh & Krishnan (2015) findings revealed that transformational leadership's role is essential in enhancing employee engagement. (Wang et al., 2011) findings confirmed that transformational leadership had a positive impact on employee performance across cultures. Avolio

& Bass (1991) conducted a study on empirical support findings revealed that transformational leadership predicts employee performance and organizational outcomes. Bass (1985) conducted a study on transformational leadership findings revealed that transformational leaders emphasized idealized influence, indicating that leaders act as role models, earning respect and trust. Research also revealed that inspirational leaders communicate a compelling vision and inspiring teams, whereas intellectual stimulation leaders encourage innovation and creative problem-solving and individualized consideration and that leaders constantly mentor and support individual growth.

Research questions:

1. Does autocratic leadership affect crisis resolution speed?
2. Does transformational leadership influence employee satisfaction?
3. How does laissez-faire leadership impact crisis management effectiveness?

Research Objectives:

1. Assess impact of leadership styles on crisis management effectiveness.
2. Evaluate employee satisfaction under different leadership styles.
3. Identify most effective leadership approach for sustainable crisis resolution.

Variables:

Independent Variables: Leadership style-autocratic leaders, transformational leaders and laissez-faire leaders.

Dependent Variables: Crisis resolution speed, employee satisfaction and crisis management effectiveness.

Hypotheses:

Ha₁: Autocratic leadership leads to faster crisis resolution compared to transformational leadership.

Ha₂: Transformational leadership results in higher employee satisfaction compared to autocratic and laissez-faire leadership.

Ha₃: Laissez-faire leadership is less effective in crisis management compared to autocratic and transformational leadership.

Ha₄: Transformational leadership will be more effective and will show significantly better outcomes than autocratic and laissez-faire styles.

Sample:

Data was gathered using convenient sampling method. The participants comprised of 150 leaders from manufacturing firms facing quality crises. Sample consisted of autocratic leaders 50, laissez-Faire 50 and transformational leaders 50 who were facing crisis management were considered in the study. The research was conducted by a self-reported survey which included two questionnaires. Pre and post crisis management was analysed.

Tools:

Consent form was given to the participants, all participants were provided with detailed information on the research, it's purpose and voluntary participation. In-order to assess leadership style, Bass, B.M., & Avolio, B.J.(1995) Multifactor leadership questionnaire, was used to categorize leaders into autocratic, transformational and laissez-faire styles. Gallup's (2020) employee engagement survey was used to identify employee satisfaction, which measured engagement and satisfaction among employees and Crisis resolution metrics (2023) were used to consider the measure of time taken and quality improvement that occurred in post-crisis.

Methodology:

Quantitative survey-based design was used in the study. Data collection for the study included comprehensive questionnaires. Rapport was established with the respondents and informed consent was taken where the researchers explained the confidentiality of responses and voluntary participation was accepted. Participants were requested to fill the questionnaires. Test instructions were clearly read out, explained and any ambiguity was clarified. Participants completed the questionnaires in one session. Scoring of different scales was done manually as per the test manual.

Sample: A sample size of 150 leaders belonging to different leadership styles, and 300 employees across industries in crisis management were considered in the study.

Statistical Analysis: Data was analysed on 150 managers and 300 employees. In-order to test the hypotheses pertaining to leadership styles in crisis management statistical analysis such as Pearson correlation, t test and ANOVA was used. To

measure the relationship between leadership styles and outcomes, Pearson correlation was administered. To check the significant differences between leadership styles independent samples t-test and One-way ANOVA was used to compare differences across all three styles of leadership. P value <0.05 and <0.01 was taken to identify the statistical significance. Statistical analysis was done using software SPSS version 24.0 Descriptive and thematic analysis were employed for qualitative data analysis.

Analysis and Discussion:

Transformational leadership excels in crisis as it can lead to high satisfaction and bring about sustainable resolution. Autocratic leaders shows speed but risks sustainability. Laissez-faire leadership is least effective. Findings reveal that Transformational leaders inspire and motivate employees, fostering commitment and extra effort. Leaders' vision and support boost employee performance.

Table 1.1 Leadership Style, Correlation, t-test & ANOVA

Leadership Style	Mean Score	SD	Correlation	t-test (p-value)	ANOVA (F,p-value)
Autocratic	3.2	1.1	r = 0.8 speed p<0.01**		F = 12.5, p<0.01
Transformational	4.5	0.8	r = 0.85 sustainability p<0.01**	t=2.35 p<0.05*	
Laissez-faire	2.1	1.3	r = 0.9 ineffectiveness p<0.01**	t=3.12, p<0.01**	

A perusal of table 1.1 and statistical data analysis revealed that a strong positive correlation ($r=0.8$, $p<0.01$) was observed between autocratic style and crisis resolution speed. It can be proved that autocratic leadership is associated with faster crisis resolution thus proving the first hypotheses. The present study is in line with the study by Bass(1985)who found that autocratic styles can expedite decision-making in crises, thus this leadership and get good performance beyond

expectations. Strong correlation ($r=0.85$, $p<0.01$) is observed between sustainability and satisfaction. This proves that transformational leadership is linked to employee satisfaction. t test results reveal significant differences between transformational and autocratic leaders($t=2.35$ $p<0.05$). Transformational leadership has significantly higher employee satisfaction than autocratic leaders thus proving second hypotheses. The present study is in line with the

study by Judge & Piccolo (2004) meta-analysis showed that transformational leadership correlates ($r=0.81$) with higher satisfaction. Results reveal a strong correlation ($r=0.9$, $p<0.01$) between laissez-faire leadership and ineffectiveness. This finding reveals that laissez-faire leadership is less effective in crisis management. A significant difference ($t=3.12$, $p<0.01$) between transformational and laissez-faire leadership. Thus it can be proved that transformational leadership is significantly more effective than laissez-faire. The present study is in line with the study by Skogstad et al., (2007) who linked laissez-faire leadership to lower effectiveness and more conflicts among employees. Statistical analysis using ANOVA ($F=12.5$, $p<0.01$) shows a significant difference in leadership styles, this indicates that transformational leaders have better outcomes than autocratic and laissez-faire styles, whereas autocratic and laissez-faire are less effective than transformational leaders. Results highlight transformational leadership's role in driving organizational success through enhanced employee engagement and productivity. Transformational leaders inspire and motivate employees, fostering commitment and extra effort. Leaders' vision and support boost employee performance and organizational outcomes.

Conclusion:

The analysis highlights transformational leadership as most effective in crisis management, balancing speed and sustainability with high employee satisfaction. Autocratic leadership shows quicker but less sustainable results, while laissez-faire is least effective. Findings prove the hypothesis of this research.

Ha₁: Autocratic leadership leads to faster crisis resolution compared to transformational leadership ($r=0.8$, $p<0.01$) has been proved.

Ha₂: Transformational leadership results in higher employee satisfaction compared to autocratic and laissez-faire leadership, indicating a strong correlation ($r=0.85$, $p<0.01$) between sustainability and satisfaction and a significant difference is also observed ($t=2.35$ $p<0.05$) between transformational and autocratic leaders thus proving the hypotheses.

Ha₃: Laissez-faire leadership is less effective in crisis management compared to autocratic and transformational leadership. Findings reveal a strong correlation ($r=0.9$, $p<0.01$) between laissez-faire leadership and ineffectiveness. A significant difference ($t=3.12$, $p<0.01$) between transformational and laissez-faire leadership observed. Thus the hypotheses is proved.

Ha₄: Transformational leadership will be more effective and will show significantly better outcomes than autocratic and laissez-faire styles. ANOVA ($F=12.5$, $p<0.01$) shows a significant difference in leadership styles, this indicates that transformational leaders have better outcomes than autocratic and laissez-faire styles. Thus the hypothesis is supported.

Result analysis reveal that organizations should prioritize transformational leadership development to drive growth. Transformational leadership has a significant positive impact on employee performance and organizational success.

Significant Implications:

Organizations should invest in leadership development programs focusing on transformational leadership skills through workshops and coaching. It is essential to balance speed and empathy during crisis. HR practices should align with transformational leadership principles in-order to boost employee performance. It is necessary to foster employee commitment and engagement to reduce in-order turnover. It is essential requirement to boost

performance and encourage leaders to inspire and motivate teams. Transformational leadership can be a key differentiator in competitive markets.

Limitations:

Sample is limited to Indian corporates; generalizability to other contexts is needed. Industry-specific biases may exist, long term impact is unclear. Self-report measures may introduce bias.

Suggestions for Future Research:

Longitudinal studies to investigate the long-term effects types of leadership on organizational outcomes. Cross-Cultural Comparisons across cultures and countries. Explore sector-specific leadership dynamics.

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